

here: Appendix for the Application of Lemenkova Polina, M.Sc for
*Scientific and Technological Research Council of Turkey (TÜBİTAK),
Research Fellowship for Foreign Citizens (Code 2216) for the research stay at the
Ege Üniversitesi Coğrafya Bölümü (Ege University, Faculty of Geography)*

duration: Two months in 2012 (01st of May - 30th of June)

Research Plan

for the research stay of the visiting researcher Lemenkova Polina, M.Sc in *Ege Üniversitesi Coğrafya Bölümü*, in the two-month time span in 2012, under the joint supervision of Prof. Dr. Ertug ONER and Assoc. Prof. Dr. Kirami OLGEM.

The reason of joint collaboration and co-supervision lies in the multi-disciplinary project which requires both technical GIS skills and specialized knowledge of geomorphological-ecological settings of the Izmir region.

Prof. Dr. Ertug ONER would support physical-geographical part of the research and supervise evaluation of the recent changes in environmental and geomorphological settings in Izmir surroundings. His knowledge of the local geomorphological and ecological phenomena in western Anatolian province will help us to assess geomorphic and environmental changes that are not obvious in the satellite data.

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Kirami OLGEM is a specialist in GIS and remote sensing data processing. His technical skills will be helpful in GIS and RS part of the research, data incorporating, collecting, processing and any professional discussion and consultations as well as cartographic presentation and mapping.

We plan to publish our results in a joint co-authorship, as a scientific paper in a peer-review journal (the exact journal title is to be discussed) and to keep contact for participation in related conferences in geo-sciences in the future.

Research topic: Application of remote sensing data & GIS methods for spatial analysis of environmental landscape changes: case study of Izmir, Turkey.

Research area: west Anatolian province (Izmir surroundings) of Anatolian Plateau, Turkey

Introduction and actuality of research problem:

The study region of Izmir and its surroundings is known for the unique and rich physical geography and environmental settings. The physical geography of the region combines diverse landforms, various geomorphological and natural landscapes, species and vegetation richness. The geomorphological settings of the area include wide variety of landforms, including mountains landscapes, caves, islands in the coastal area, waterfalls, lakes, etc. The geology of the area of Western Anatolia is characterized by the neotectonic active faulting and high seismicity, which leads to geomorphological instabilities and landslide formation in the research area. At the same time, the region is being intensively visited by the tourists, due to its natural attractiveness, favorable climatic conditions, scenic landscapes and cultural richness. The development of the tourism covers both traditional coastal areas and geothermal hot water springs. Besides recreation activities, the region is known for its intensive agricultural cultivation, such as producing olive trees, cultivating fruits.

Finally, being a large metropolis of Turkey, Izmir is an important industrial city, a key seaport in the transportation network in the Mediterranean, and a country's business center. All these factors cause strong anthropogenic pressure on the environment in the study region of Izmir. Therefore, the purpose of this research is to analyze, how the environmental settings and landscapes in Izmir province changed over the past decades.

Research aims:

- 1) Ecoregions of Anatolian Plateau, Turkey: comparison and brief overview
- 2) Environmental mapping of mountainous landscapes (western Anatolia)
- 3) Spatial analysis of land cover types in western Anatolian province
- 4) One publication of the research results in a scientific journal
or one poster for presentation at upcoming environmental conference

Expected results:

- Analysis of the landscape changes in west Anatolian province (Izmir surroundings):
- Thematic map of the land cover types in west Anatolian province, Izmir
- Report for the TÜBİTAK resuming results of the research work
- An article reporting the outcome of the research work published in peer-reviewed journal (environment or earth sciences) or poster for presentation on a geoscience conference

Research GIS data:

Data collecting. Main geo-data materials will be taken from the GIS open sources. These include aerial and satellite images covering different time span (10-20 years). Among available open sources we consider the following ones: satellite imagery from The Earth Explorer (<http://edcns17.cr.usgs.gov/NewEarthExplorer/>), The Earth Science Data Interface (<http://glcfapp.glc.f.umd.edu:8080/esdi/index.jsp>), GloVis (<http://glovis.usgs.gov/>), aerial images (Google Earth), free Digital Elevation Models from the open source <http://geomorphometry.org/>, ASTER GDEM www.gdem.aster.ersdac.or.jp/. Additionally, other available geodata may be used as well: descriptive data, shape files, materials from the faculty and Ege university library (maps, books, reports and articles).

Technical background:

The research is technically based on *Quantum GIS* and *ILWIS* software for raster processing and geodata modeling. The *ArcGIS* can be used as well (depending on the available license).

Detailed research plan (scheduled on two-week periods)

§ 1. 01 May – 15 May: Data organizing, starting GIS project

1. Data collecting. The first, initial part of the research working plan includes:

- organizing collected geodata on the faculty's computer (on hard disk);
 - discussing, overviewing and assessment of these materials with supervisors and colleagues in order to become familiar with all available resources;
 - starting GIS project, geo-referencing (if necessary), organizing geodata in ArcGIS / ILWIS
2. Data organizing. Preparing GIS project with remote sensing data and basic vector ground layers for GIS mapping (§ 3):
- Ground layer showing relief, based on DEM, geological and topographic maps
 - Urban main infrastructure of Izmir city and surrounding: street network, buildings, etc.
 - Land cover types and vegetation covering test sites in the surrounding mountains
 - Satellite images of the research area taken in different time (last 20-30 years)

§ 2. 15 May – 01 June: Spatial analysis in GIS project

- Spatial analysis of the thematic layers.
Spatial analysis of the geodata is aimed to perform physical-geographical overview and landscapes of the western Anatolian Plateau, as well as to analyze distribution of various land use types over regions of western Anatolian province of the Anatolian plateau, Turkey

- Preparing thematic layers in *ArcGIS* and/or *ILWIS*: Geomorphological relief of western Anatolia, based on DEM and analysis of landscapes and land cover types
- Performing image processing using supervised classification (ILWIS) for indication of land cover types in the western Anatolian Plateau
- Environmental change detection: overlay of geodata (maps, satellite images and DEMs) using cartographic methods, to compare changes in landscape patterns at present and 10-20 years ago (time span 1990 – 2010).
- Environmental corridors: regional studies of natural land cover types in Izmir province, typical for the test areas. Detection of changes in green patches and vegetation coverage. Application of the supervised classification (e.g., max. likelihood) to characterize main vegetation types in the surroundings mountains, and its dynamics (whether it is extending or regressing over time)

§ 3. 01 June – 15 June: Thematic mapping: land cover types in Anatolian Plateau

Thematic mapping is based on ILWIS / Arc GIS, using the results of the previous working step (§ 2, Spatial analysis...): visualizing changes in landscape structures and land cover during the last decades (before and after great political changes) using overlay. Preparing final layouts.

- Regional studies of western Anatolian province, Izmir surroundings: land cover types & landscape patterns
- Creating thematic maps detecting landscape dynamics since 1990
- Creating thematic maps demonstrating land cover types over the research area.

§ 4. 15 June – 30 June: Preparing final report writing paper for publication

1. The cartographic results should be visualized as 1-2 maps illustrating dynamics in land types in Izmir province, caused by global environmental and anthropogenic pressure since 1990s.
2. Writing article for the publication in a scientific journal: “*Environmental landscapes changes in western Anatolian province, Izmir, Turkey*”.
3. Preparing final report for the TÜBİTAK, Ankara.

6th of October, 2011.

Scientific supervisors:
Prof. Dr. Ertug ONER
Yrd. Doç. Dr. M. Kirami ÖLGEN

Visiting researcher:
Polina Lemenkova, M.Sc,
PhD student at TU Dresden

Literature used:

- Ataberk E. & Baykal F. (2011). Utilization of natural and cultural resources of Dikili (Izmir) for tourism. The 2nd International Geography Symposium GEOMED 2010. *Procedia Social and Behavioral Sciences* 19, 173–180
- Emekli G. & F. Baykal (2011). Opportunities of utilizing natural and cultural resources of Bornova (Izmir) through tourism. *Procedia Social and Behavioral Sciences* 19, 181–189
- Göktürkler G., Balkaya Ç., Erhan Z. (2008). Geophysical investigation of a landslide: The Altındağ landslide site, İzmir (western Turkey). *Journal of Applied Geophysics* 65, 84–96
- Serpen U. (2004). Hydrogeological investigations on Balçova geothermal system in Turkey. *Geothermics* 33, 309–335
- Web articles: Izmir (General information); <http://en.wikipedia.org>; Geography of Turkey. <http://en.wikipedia.org>